

Marital Discord: A Glance at Anita Desai's Novel "Fire on the Hill".

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Abstract:

Anita Desai's "Forest Fire" deserves an ecological philosophy. Anita Desai mostly focuses on relationships in her writing. The problem of friction arises from marital conflict and lack of understanding between men and women. However, a survival side to his job is also very important. She presents her character through often conflicting couples, a sensitive wife, and a negative husband. It would be apt to say that marriage, a vital issue challenged in the traditional society, marriage is a patriarchal instrument which leads a woman to subjugation and slavery. It is also noticed that the predicament of a married woman has several shades. In martial issues sex proves to be a brutal punishment for such child brides who nevertheless did not revolt but on the other hand continued to suffer and helped to perpetuate such oppression.

It is seen that the female characters in her works are generally neurotic and sensitive by nature, almost in conflict with other areas such as husband and wife and the environment. Therefore, marital discord is prominent in most of Desai's novels. The psychological and experiential causes of this conflict may vary from character to character. Women's writing continues to occupy an important place for more than one reason.

It asks for ideas to understand the importance of patriarchy. The work of all women is not necessarily feminist. But feminist narratives can emerge from absence and denial. Depressions of Indian women, marital discord, survival, issues are the main themes of feminist writing.

Women's self-discovery has always been a favorite theme of many female novelists.

Keywords: personal consciousness, predicament, oppression, marital discord, sensitivity.

Objectives:

- 1) To study the dilemmas of women in marital lives.
- 2) To study suppressions and oppressions of women and try to assert their individuality.

Introduction:

Conflict in marriage is as old as the institution of marriage itself, although it differs from time to time and differs from person to person. The union of married men and women in the pre-industrial era in terms of culture, cooperation, trust, and religion favors the individual and thus provides better family relations. There is tension and dysfunction in their marriage as well, but their belief in justice and faith, their financial dependence, and fear of disapproval hold them together. After the Industrial Revolution, marital disputes became more important. Men and women do not have knowledge of all aspects of sexual, psychological, spiritual and social life, and do not have the understanding that can bring peace, harmony and self-regulation.

The increasing independence of married women in the industrial age drove them further and changed the concept of marriage, "from stability, eternal life, and disharmony to discord, separation, and divorce," in the words of Virendra Kumar. Marriage conflict represents the separation of consent and cooperation between spouses. Most often, marital discord occurs when there is rivalry between spouses through internal and external events such as separation, physical abuse, and nickname-taking. They stay away when they cannot resolve the issues that cause stress and anxiety in their relation-

ships. Marriage conflict is a recurring theme in Anita Desai's novels. Their stories of feminist anxieties show failed marriages, often resulting in isolation and loneliness. "Cry the Peacock", "Where are you going this summer?" Sahitya's Academy Award-winning novel, *The Fire on the Hill*, was published in 1972. His novel, *Fire on the Hill*

, is about communication and lack of understanding in married life. The woman's mental retreat reflects the landscape -

rocky and barren. His desire for solitude and solitude can be seen in his dislike of his bride holding him. "Let me go!" she shouted, I did all my duties. Unloading" (30).

Carignano gave him an anonymous name and escaped at will. Mrinalini Solunki believes that the choice of complete isolation has nothing to do with the spirituality of Indian thought. He didn't choose this breakup willingly, but the situation left him no choice. Being intertwined with people and the business world for a long time left her with no sense of interest and belonging. Therefore, she chose to stay away from the world of information and visitors in order to survive. "

The novel is about a fraud that Nanda is forced to commit. His marriage was not happy. It's not all love and generosity, but her husband's betrayal makes her life quiet. Children are strangers. Grace and grandeur are now designed to drive.

"Her relationship with her husband does not contain her. She directs her own life: she lies to Raqqa about everything.

Her husband does not love her, loves her, resists, hin

ders her like a queen - everything she does. Not because she is a Christian, but because she is a believer, she loves her life. He was quiet when he had an affair with his maths teacher, Miss David, whom he married because he was someone he loved the whole time. The children were different from his situation. He does not understand and does not like them. He is not alone here with his own choice - here because that is what he was forced to do, what he was forced to do. Another unresolved relationship - the one between Raka's mother and her alcoholic, violent father - emerges in the novel. However, the author focuses on the plight of Nanda Kaul, who was cheated on and betrayed by her husband. "Misunderstanding of spouse's expectations and anger are the cause of marital discord in Ms. Kaur". That's why Anita Desai teaches him through the characters of his wife against unhappy marriage in the fake world. "Fire on the Hill" is Anita Desai's fifth novel. In this novel, she especially deals with the relations and conflicts between husband and wife. Conflict in drama is one of the main themes of the novel. Nanda Kaul is a woman with the role and responsibility of the Vice Chancellor of the University of Punjab. She has a busy schedule, although there are many maids around. He was known for his hospitality, but he felt suffocated. Marriage conflict is the absence of change and unity in marriage. It shows the breakdown of commitment and cooperation between spouses. In most cases, marital incompatibility is a conflict between the spouses caused by internal and external events at a fixed point, physical violence, fear of abandonment, etc. It is a process that starts before the physical separation and continues after the marriage ends. Marital conflict is a very stressful situation that can push people to the level of insanity or engage in behaviors that cause them to have psychotic or hysterical responses. It is an important predictor of subsequent guilt and depressive symptoms in married couples. It is clear that marital problems are more likely to cause depression than depression causes marital problems. Although marriage varies from person to person, it is not as old as the institution of marriage itself. In the pre-industrial era, married men and women shared common values, common interests, beliefs and hopes, and personal preferences for the family, thereby creating family relationships. There is a lot of stress in their marriage, women suffer from immaturity but here there are morals and beliefs, financial beliefs and fear of social punishment. Marriage disputes are strong grounds for termination of spousal rights. However, where divorce is rare and stigmatized, we would not expect divorce to lead to conflict.

In India, for example, the separation of marriages does not occur due to a lack of emotional harmony, but may require a more serious or at least a marriage to be identified as a serious conflict. Conflict in marriage is not new in India, it has existed in every epoch of known history. But it is only used for separation in severe cases such as unexpected violence, abandonment, mental illness, pregnancy, and injustice. Marriage disputes became more important after the Industrial Rebellion. Men and women who come together in marriage do not have knowledge about many psychological and social aspects of life, they do not have the understanding, ability to adapt, and self-control that will lead to good behavior. In the industrial age, the married woman became independent, distanced her from harmony and changed the understanding of marriage. In the words of Virendra Kumar, "From Fixed, Stubborn and Insoluble to Dispute, Separation and Divorce" (Kumar. 1978:25). Regular marriages can lead to dissatisfaction between spouses, which leads people to consider alternative marriages. For example, a person forced into an arranged marriage may not be impressed and may try to live independently. A conflicted marriage can have a negative impact on a child's development. One of the biggest fears of children is that their parents will leave. The concept of arranged marriage is a modern document and may come from England, America or India. Nayantara Sahgal is one of the main themes in the work of Kamala Markandaya, Virginia Woolf, Raja Rao, Bhabani Bhattacharya, Anita Desai, and others. Anita Desai mentions in her article that marital discord is a serious problem. He humbly admits that he's unfit for social media writing. However, it becomes entangled in marital discord and leads to insincerity, infidelity, and a soul-destroying reconciliation process. Choosing marital conflict as the theme, Anita Desai shows the inability to share the soul and the fear and pain that white can cause in communication between the couple. Different attitudes, personal difficulties and fears lead to conflicts and conflicts between couples. In all her stories, we experience the trauma of married life. Each novel features and presents the essential features of a conflicted marriage, and Mrs. Desai gives them new ideas and pictures. She boldly points out that marriage in society generally follows the law of the jungle of survival of the fittest and survival of the fittest. Marriage conflicts in his novels focus on relationships. Too many restrictions and height restrictions on a girl who has just been separated from her parents hit her brain and caused a lot of stress. This stress can cause suicidal ideation, depression, marital discord, mental illness, etc. many things can happen. Therefore, society and its forbidden literature play an important role in influencing the feelings of girls.

Conclusion:

Anita Desai is today's author because she thinks about new concepts and knows how to deal with them. She explores the suffering of women in today's society. She presents her views on relationships and the human condition as the most important issue of our time. Desai cites the complexity of these relationships as one of her themes, and this is a serious problem. She tries to show the problem without interrupting, she.

Anita Desai's stories almost reflect her belief that men focus on action, knowledge, and success, while female writers focus more on thoughts, feelings, and emotions. Therefore, all of the above are common problems in marriage. While these are problems, there can also be hope for growth, learning, and reconciliation. Although these problems are still difficulties leading to marriage, they are magnified by the behavior of men and women. The result of this difference may be a decline in social relationships and a decrease in the average mental health level of the population. It should not be forgotten that managing the divorce path does not solve the main problem because there are problems such as divorce in long-term marriages of married couples. In general, the health of the next generation will improve if there are changes in society or politics that lead to more children being raised by parents with stable and harmonious marriages. A crucial theme in Anita Desai's work, marital conflict has deep roots in her work. We cannot find a novel that escapes this conflict. People always seek fulfillment and fulfillment through love and friendship. Without it, an emptiness forms in their lives and beauty and charm are taken from them. They have lost their ability to survive. Maya, Monisha or Raqqa are all victims of bad marriages and relationships. Their lives would be easier and happier if they didn't experience some harmony and love with their partner. The key to a successful marriage is love, understanding, mutual respect, trust, commitment and togetherness. While many couples can find all the important elements in their marriage, others find that one or more of the elements are missing in their relationship. This can always lead to unexpected or undesirable results. For this reason, many couples face negative consequences such as divorce. The main reason why married couples see marriage as a good relationship is that they experience insecurity, respect, love and understanding problems in their relationships. In Anita Desai's novels, it is seen that the destruction in the world of marriage is mostly caused by conflict.

What Desai wants is a balance between facts and opinions, which is the only way to resolve marital disputes. This is a question that bothers me every day. It is also a serious problem today and we need to find many solutions to make life satisfying and balanced.

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